

The family Tornidae (Gastropoda, Risssooidea) in the East Atlantic, 2. Circulinae

La familia Tornidae (Gastropoda, Risssooidea) en el Atlántico oriental, 2. Circulinae

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ABSTRACT

The species of the subfamily Circulininae from the East Atlantic belonging to the genus *Circulus* are studied. There is a total of 8 species, of which 2 are previously undescribed. The shell morphology is illustrated for all the species with scanning electron micrographs which show the protoconch and, in some cases, the microsculpture.

RESUMEN

Se estudian las especies del género *Circulus* de la subfamilia Circulininae del Atlántico occidental. En total son 8 especies, de las cuales 2 son nuevas para la ciencia. De todas ellas se ilustra la morfología de la concha con microscopía electrónica de barrido, incluyendo la protoconcha y, en algunos casos, la microescultura.

INTRODUCTION

In their 1969 paper, ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969) studied the small discoid species then scarcely known from the West African coast. Subsequently, new species were described (ROLÁN AND RUBIO, 1991, 1996; RUBIO AND ROLÁN, 1991; ROLÁN, RUBIO AND RYALL, 2000; ROLÁN AND RYALL, 2002). ROLÁN AND RUBIO (2002) published a paper on the species of the family Tornidae Sacco 1986, from West Africa reviewing and illustrating 39 species of which 23 were new to science.

More recently, BOUCHET AND ROCROI (2005) recorded the Gastropod taxa of family level and listed as accepted the family Tornidae with the following subfamilies: Torninae Sacco, 1884; Circulinae Fretter and Graham, 1962; Teinos-

tomatinae Cossmann, 1917; Vitrinellinae Bush, 1897.

In the above mentioned work on the Tornidae from West Africa (ROLÁN AND RUBIO, 2002), the family had been studied somewhat incompletely because some of these subfamilies were not included in Tornidae at that time but in other taxonomic groups. The genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865, was treated by FISCHER (1887: 824) as a subgenus of *Gibbula* Risso, 1826; later DALL (1927) placed it in synonymy with *Lydiphnis* Melville, 1906 and THIELE (1929) as a genus within *Cyclostrematidae*. Most of them were placed in Archaeogastropoda, and this remained so until FRETTER (1956) researched the anatomy of *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836), type

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species of *Circulus*, and noticed that the radula of this species was taenioglossate, not rhipidoglossate.

For this reason we have resumed the study of the family Tornidae with the intention of reviewing the subfamilies not included in the previous study. In the present work we begin with subfamily Circulinae.

In the present work, as well as in the previous ones, we intend to show a complete iconography of the species pointing out the differential morphological characters which allow a clear placement of each taxon.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material studied comes from several collections made by the authors, mainly in the Mediterranean, Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal, São Tomé and Príncipe, Annobón and Angola. Other material collected by other malacologists such as Francisco Fernandes, Anselmo Peñas, Peter Ryall and José María Hernández was also examined. There is also some material from the Muséum National d' Histoire Naturelle of Paris (MNHN).

The material was collected mainly from sediments from the intertidal level to 8-10 m, while diving with snorkel and SCUBA diving, and also by dredging from a boat. The material from the MNHN was collected in several expeditions to Guinea Conakry, Ivory Coast

and Congo with R/V "André Nizery" and "Antea Benchaci I", and in Angola (coll. Serge Gofas) through manual dredging.

The sediments were sieved and examined under a binocular microscope either by the collectors or the authors.

The numbering of the protoconch whorls was made following the method of VERDUIN (1976) in which the whorls are counted following an initial nucleus.

Abbreviations

AMNH American Museum of Natural History, New York
MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid
MNHN Muséum national d' Histoire naturelle, Paris
MHNS Museo de Historia Natural, Universidad, Santiago de Compostela
NHMUK The Natural History Museum, London
RBINS Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Bruxelles
ZMB Zoologisch Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin
CAP collection of Anselmo Peñas, Vilanova i la Geltrú
CDO collection of Daniel Oliver, Madrid
CPR collection of Peter Ryall, Maria Rain
CJH collection of José María Hernández, Gáldar
sp specimen with soft parts
s shell empty
f fragment

RESULTS

Family TORNIDAE Subfamily CIRCULINAE Fretter and Graham, 1962 Genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865

Circulus Jeffreys, 1865. *Brit. Conch.*, vol 3: 315 [established as a subgenus of *Trochus*; type species: *Delphinula duminyi* Requier, 1848 = *Circulus striatus*].

General characters of the shell: Protoconch: multispiral without any sculpture. The transition to the teleoconch is difficult to observe, because the separation is

scarcely apparent. The beginning of the teleoconch may be observed by looking at the beginning of the spiral cords, although sometimes these are eroded.

Teloconch: circular, flat, with a wide deep umbilicus. Spiral ornamentation formed by spiral cords. Some of them are prominent, forming keels. They lack any axial sculpture except for growth lines.

In order to describe more easily the sculpture of the shell in view of its taxonomic importance, we can represent the apertural peristome as a hexagon (Fig. 1) (even though its shape is frequently irregular, tending sometimes to be rectangular or circular):

- 1: Adapical insertion of the external lip with the shell
- 1-2: Subsutural cords
- 2: Cord/upper keel
- 2-3: Lateral upper cords
- 3: Cord/peripheral keel
- 3-4: Lateral lower cords

- 4: Cord/basal keel
- 4-5: Basal cords
- 5: periumbilical cord (change of direction)

5-6: Umbilical cords
6: Abapical insertion of the external lip in the shell

6-1: Callus: the callus is a simple prolongation of the inner part on the columella.

It is important to mention that the border of the external lip touches the teloconch a little above the peripheral keel (3) while the internal border does it a little above the basal keel (4).

Some species may lack some of these cords-keels, or additional cord-keels may appear. Also some intraspecific variability can be observed.

Dichotomous key of *Circulus*:

- 1. - Shell with smooth spire. There are only umbilical cords *C. senegalensis*
- Shell with spiral cords /or keels 2
- 2 - Shell without keels 3
- Shell with keels 4
- 3 - Shell with evident spiral and basal cords *C. congoensis*
- Shell with lateral and basal areas without spiral cords or cords only appreciable under magnification *C. striatus*
- 4 - Peripheral keel clearly more developed than the basal keel 5
- Shell with the basal keel as developed or more than the peripheral keel 6
- 5 - Shell with vitreous aspect, without basal keel and without subsutural cords *C. pseudopraecedens*
- Shell of white color with basal cord/keel less developed than the peripheral one and with subsutural clear cords *C. ryalli*
- 6 - Shell lacking lower lateral cords with a basal keel more developed than the peripheral one *C. stephani*
- Lower lateral cords present 7
- 7 - Peristome tending to be rectangular and having microsculpture under magnification *C. microsculpturatus*
- Peristome subcircular, lower lateral cords, tending to form subperipheral keels *C. smithi*

Circulus striatus (Philippi, 1836) (Figs. 2A-G, 3A-G, 4A-G)

Valvata striata Philippi, 1836, p. 147, pl. IX, fig. 3A-C. [Type locality: Cefalù near Catania, Sicily, Pleistocene]

Adeorbis tricarinatus Wood, 1848. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* 9: 530.

Delphinula duminyi Requier, 1848. *Cat. Coq. Corse*: 64 [Type locality: Ajaccio, Corsica].

- Delphinula triangulata* Rayneval and Ponzi, 1854. *Cat. Monte Mario*: 18 [Type locality: Monte Mario near Rome, Italy, Pleistocene]
- Skenea striatula* Weinkauff, 1862. *J. Conch.* 10: 343 [incorrect subsequent spelling of *striata* Philippi, 1836].
- Circulus costulatus* Locard, 1889. *Bull. Soc. Mal. France*, 6: 297. [Type locality: France: Brest, Morbihan and Vendée].
- Circulus carinulatus* Locard, 1889. *Bull. Soc. Mal. France*, 6: 300. [Regions armoricaine and aquitaine; Provence].
- Circulus striatus bicarinatus* Altimira, 1977: 25. [Type locality: Sant Pol de Mar, Barcelona].
- Delphinula costata* Danilo and Sandri, 1856.

Type material: Probably in ZMB.

Other material examined: Usual form: Spain: 1 s, Santander (MHNS); 2 s, Ria de Vigo, 10 m (MHNS); 2 s, Tarragona (CAP); 5 s, Denia (beached) (MHNS); 133 s, 11 f, Cullera (beached) (CDO); 16 s, Denia (beached) (CDO); 18 s, Oliva (beached) (CDO); 6 s, Jávea (beached) (CDO); 2 s, Ibiza (CDO). Morocco: 3 s, Agadir (MHNS). Carinate form: Spain: 7 s, Cullera (beached) (CDO). Tricarinate form: Spain: 3 s, Cullera (beached) (CDO).

Description: Shell (Figs. 2A-E, 3A-E): the best description can be seen in FRETTER AND GRAHAM (1978). Shell flat with about 4 whorls (including protoconch) reaching 1.6 mm in diameter and 0.8 mm in height; shells with five whorls reaching 2.75 mm diameter and 1.25 mm height respectively (GRAHAM, 1988).

The protoconch (Figs. 2F, 3F, 4F-G) is multispiral, has a little less than 2.25 whorls, and is about 390 μ m in width. It is smooth without any ornamentation and its end is barely marked with a light line coincident with the beginning of the spiral cords of the teleoconch.

The shell with typical morphology has spiral cords not forming keels. Apically 6-7 spiral cords can be observed whose width is approximately half that of the corresponding interspaces. The subsutural adapical one is weak, a little deep and limited on both sides by granules. Below, there are three more similar cords; the lowest one situated on the upper keel. Below these, there are four more cords (upper laterals) the fourth being in the emplacement of the peripheral keel.

Examined from the umbilical side, the shell has very weak low lateral cords, which in some shells give the impression that there are no cords, up to an isolated cord, situated in the position of the basal keel and which may sometimes be double. Apparently, there are no basal cords between the basal keel and the umbilical cords, the latter being always present and evident under mag-

nification of the umbilicus. The lack of basal cords may be caused by erosion or they may decrease as the shell grows.

There are four or five umbilical cords, separated by sulci and crossed by an axial irregular and granulose sculpture. The aperture is circular.

The operculum is corneous and rounded.

The animal of *C. striatus* has been figured in FRETTER AND GRAHAM (1962: 284)

Distribution: The species is known from Ireland and the British Isles (FRETTER AND GRAHAM, 1978; GRAHAM, 1982, 1988), Atlantic Iberian Peninsula (ROLÁN, 1983); Portugal (NOBRE, 1940); Mediterranean (HIDALGO, 1917; POPPE AND GOTO, 1991). The record from São Tomé and Príncipe (FERNANDES AND ROLÁN, 1993), refers to another species with which it was confused at the time.

Remarks: *Adeorbis tricarinatus* Wood, 1848 was described as a species distinct from *C. striatus*. The description of this species was based on fossil shells and authors like JEFFREYS (1865) considered it, as well as *C. supranitidus* (Wood, 1848), a fossil variety of *C. striatus*. In spite of this opinion, even recently some authors, such as TERRENI (1981) consider it valid. AARTSEN, MENHORST AND GITTEBERGER (1984, fig. 57) indicate that this taxon as dubious, but admit that it could be valid and compare it to other similar fossil species. COPPINI, CUNEO, MARGELLI AND CAMPANI (2005, fig. 2c) present a similar shell and consider that it is a valid species

Figure 1. Schematic images showing the different sculpture and the terms employed for these characters.

Figura 1. Imágenes esquemáticas mostrando los distintos tipos de escultura y la terminología empleada para estos caracteres.

which is called *Circulus tricarinatus*. This is reflected in the CLEMAM web page where this name is also mentioned as valid.

In Cullera (Valencia, East Spain), a great quantity of material of *Circulus*

striatus has been collected. In this material, there were many shells which do not represent exactly the typical form of the species, but have some peculiar characters instead: a form, which is carinate

Figure 2. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A-E: shells, 1.6, 1.6, 1.5, 1.2, 1.2 mm, Cullera, Valencia; F: protoconch; G: detail of the umbilicus.

Figura 2. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A-E: conchas, 1,6; 1,6; 1,5; 1,2; 1,2 mm, Cullera, Valencia; F: protoconcha; G: detalle del ombligo.

Figure 3. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A-C: shells, 1.68, 1.7, 1.9 mm, Agadir, Morocco (MHNS); D, E: shells, 1.9, 2.1 mm, from Tarragona (CAP); F: protoconch, Agadir; G: detail of the microsculpture, Tarragona.

Figura 3. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A-C: conchas, 1,68; 1,7; 1,9 mm, Agadir, Marruecos (MHNS); D, E: conchas, 1,9; 2,1 mm, de Tarragona (CAP); F: protoconcha, Agadir; G: detalle de la microescultura, Tarragona.

Figure 4. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A, B: shells of carinate form 1.24, 1.4 mm (CDO); C-E: shells of tricarinate form, 1.9, 1.5, 1.7 mm, Cullera, Valencia (CDO); F, G: protoconchs.

Figura 4. *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). A, B: conchas de la forma con quilla, 1,24; 1,4 mm (CDO); C-E: conchas de la forma con tres quillas, 1,9; 1,5; 1,7 mm, Cullera, Valencia (CDO); F, G: protoconchas.

(Fig. 4A-B), has a more developed peripheral cord/keel; another form, is tricarinate (Figs. 4C-E) presenting three cords more developed in the shape of a keel. These cords are placed in the upper position (2), peripheral position

(3) and basal position (4). The presence of these different forms in only a small area suggests to us that they are simply extreme forms or variants of one species, *Circulus striatus* with variable development of the keels.

Circulus smithi Bush, 1897 (Figs. 5A-E, 6A-F, 7A-D)

Cyclostrema tricarinata Smith, E. A., 1871. p. 737, pl.75, fig. 26. [Type locality: Whydah, Dahomey]. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. New name for *Cyclostrema tricarinatus* Smith 1871, non *Adeorbis tricarinatus* Wood 1842. p. 126.

Type material: Probably in BMNH. Not examined.

Other material examined: Western Sahara: 4 s, 3 j, Dakhla, 50-60 m, (MHNS). Mauritania: 8 s, Nouakchott, 80-100 m (CJH). Ivory Coast: 1 j, off Grand Bassam, R/V "Antea Benchaci I", 5° 11,3' N, 3° 46' W, (MNHN); 3 s, off Grand Bassam R/V "Antea Benchaci I" I, 30 m, 5° 09,2' N, 3° 47,1' W (MNHN). Ghana: 30 s, 13 j, 8 f, Miamia, 38-40 m (MHNS); 8 j, 8 f, Miamia, 45-55 m (MHNS). Angola: 1 s, Luanda, 50 m (MHNS); 22 s, 1 f, Luanda, 20-100 m (MHNS).

Description: Shell (Figs. 5A-C, 6A-D, 7A-D) flat reaching 1.8 mm in diameter, with 4.1 whorls (protoconch included) and height of about 0.86 mm. In lateral view, the first whorls barely extend beyond the level of the last whorl, although this character is somewhat variable.

The protoconch (Figs. 5D, 6E-F) is smooth with 2 ½ whorls, and about 560 µm in diameter. Well preserved protoconchs may show very fine slightly sinusoidal growth lines. The teleoconch begins with a not very noticeable line, slightly sinusoidal, and with the onset of the spiral cords. In some shells the protoconch seems to have more whorls due to the fact that the first whorl of the teleoconch is practically smooth. In such shells, the transition to the protoconch is not clear, but can be seen as the subsutural cord continues parallel to the suture and the other cords appear progressively below, sometimes after a new interruption as a scar, where they are more evident.

As in other *Circulus*, the shell sculpture consists of spiral cords which are narrower than their interspaces (Fig. 5E). Growth lines can be seen in these interspaces. The umbilicus is wide and may present 2-3 umbilical cords in the interior, but sometimes these may be

transformed into 8-9 very fine and closely set cords.

Distribution: From Western Sahara south to Angola.

Remarks: This species presents some variability, but most of the shells have three cords which are more developed, forming keels: the upper one in position 2 (upper keel), 3 (peripheral keel) and 4 (basal keel) (see Fig. 1 for these positions). The external lip is inserted on the previous whorls a little above the peripheral keel, while the internal lip begins at the level of the lower keel. Between the suture and the upper keel there are 4-5 cords, the first one of which is very close to the suture. Between the upper keel and the peripheral one there are two cords; and between this latter and the lower one there are three or four. Occasionally, one of these cords can be more developed forming a keel above the basal one. In basal view, five basal cords can be seen.

The separation with those *C. striatus* which present more prominent peripheral keels is based mainly on the umbilical axial striation present between the umbilical cords, while *C. smithi* lacks this sculpture completely, only showing spiral cords. Furthermore, the cords of *C. striatus* have more volume than those of *C. smithi*.

Figure 5. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A-C: shells, 1.7, 1.89, 1.92 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); D: protoconch; E: details of the microsculpture.

Figura 5. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A-C: conchas, 1,7; 1,89; 1,92 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); D: protoconcha; E: detalles de la microescultura.

Figure 6. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A-D: shells, 2.9, 3.2, 2.3, 2.6 mm, Congo (MNHN); E, F: protoconchs.

Figure 6. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A-D: conchas, 2,9; 3,2; 2,3; 2,6 mm, Congo (MNHN); E, F: protoconchas.

Circulus congoensis (Thiele, 1925) (Figs. 8A-D, 9A-I)

Vitrinella congoensis Thiele, 1925. *Gast. Deut. Tiefsee Expedition*: 147, pl.9, fig. 3A-C. [Type locality: Congo mouth].

Circulus striatus in ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969): 10, fig. 5.

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 8A-C) in ZMB.

Other material studied: Western Sahara: 1 c, Dakhla (50-60 m) (MHNS); Senegal: 1 s, Casamance 12° 20,7' N, 16° 53,1' W (MNHN). Ghana: 14 s, Miamia, 38-40 m (MHNS). Guinea Conakry: 1 s, 1 j, W Ile Quito, R/V "André Nizery" Sedigui II, 10° 00' N, 15° 46' W, 28 m (MNHN); 3 s, 1 j, W Ile Quito, R/V "André Nizery" Sedigui II, 10° 00' N, 15° 58' W, 34 m (MNHN); 3 s, W Ile Quito, 10° 00' N, 15° 43' W, 26 m (MNHN); 1 s, Río Yomponi 10° 24' N, 14° 50' W, 22 m (MHNS); 3 s, Río Nuñez 10° 35,5' N, 15° 26' W 9 m (MNHN). Guinea Bissau: 1 s, Bissau II 10° 45' N, 15° 44,5' W, 25 m (MHNS); Angola: 3 s, Luanda, 20-100 m (MHNS).

Description: Shell (Figs. 8A-C, 9A-D) with 4.3 whorls (protoconch included) reaching 1.7 mm in diameter and 0.9 mm in height.

The protoconch (Figs. 8D, 9F-G) is smooth and reaches nearly three whorls and about 660-710 μ m in diameter. The spiral cords begin after a small scar.

The teleoconch is ornamented with spiral cords which are clearly narrower than the corresponding interspaces. All cords are similar in size; none of them is more developed and so they do not form any keel. Only the subsutural cord (Fig. 9H-I) is clearly narrower than the others just when it appears at the end of the protoconch, and is only visible under strong magnification. After this first whorl, this cord increases in size, its width subsequently approaching that of the other cords.

The shell has a little more than 20 spiral cords: 7-8 from the suture to the place where the basal keel (which does not exist) would be; about ten in the basal area and 5-6 more inside the umbilicus. The cords are a little more flat at the base than at the dorsal area.

The larger shells, like the holotype, may have fewer cords or they may be less apparent.

Distribution: This species is known from the Western Sahara south to Angola.

Remarks: When ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969) reviewed the taxon *Circulus striatus* from West Africa, they mixed up more than one species. They studied 21 shells from 7 localities, 14 of which from Cotonou (Dahomey). They described

and figured as *C. striatus* the only shell from Iles de Los, West of Crawford Banc, which in our opinion does not belong to this species but to another that we will describe below. They compared the shells from Cotonou, which were also illustrated, commenting that they could correspond to *Vitrinella congoensis* Thiele, 1925, but considering it as a variety of *C. striatus*. After examining the photographs of the holotype of *Vitrinella congoensis* Thiele in ZMB, we confirm that the shell of *V. congoensis* is really very similar to the shells represented by Adam and Knudsen as *C. striatus* from Cotonou, but in our opinion it is different from the true *C. striatus*. For this reason we consider that *V. congoensis* Thiele is a valid species of *Circulus*, different from *C. striatus*.

Probably, the confusion of Adam and Knudsen could be due to the study of a large lot of *Circulus* (approximately 150 shells) from Arcachon in the Dautzenberg collection. The shells in this lot (not examined by us) were apparently recent and showed great variability: some of them had a smooth base, which is usual in the typical European *C. striatus*, whereas others had a striated base and even intermediate grades appeared. Therefore, the decision of Adam and Knudsen to consider all of them (those from Arcachon and those from West Africa) as *C. striatus* is understandable in view of the low number of shells examined from some areas, their similarity and small size, and the lack of electronic microscopy.

Figure 7. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A, B: shells, 2,7, 2,7 mm, Nouakchott, Mauritania (CJH); C, D: shells, 2,2, 2,9 mm, Dakar, Senegal.

Figure 7. *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897. A, B: conchas, 2,7; 2,7 mm, Nouakchott, Mauritania (CJH); C, D: conchas, 2,2; 2,9 mm, Dakar, Senegal.

The use of electronic microscopy allowed us to evaluate that the variability in *C. striatus* could occasionally lead to consider different species (like *C. tricarinatus*). The study of many shells of *C. striatus* from the Mediterranean (Cullera, Valencia) and the Atlantic (Galicia, Morocco) showed us that those typical characters are constant and different from other species.

The most important differences between *C. striatus* and *C. congoensis* are:

1- The presence on the entire shell of a light subsutural sculptured cord in *C. striatus*. In *C. congoensis* this cordlet is barely sculptured, and it is only found at the beginning in the teleoconch, later changing into a normal cord.

2- The cords in the lateral low area and basal area in *C. congoensis* are

Figure 8. *Circulus congoensis* (Thiele, 1925). A-C: holotype, 1.93 mm, Congo mounth (ZMB); D: protoconch.

Figura 8. *Circulus congoensis* (Thiele, 1925). A-C: holotipo, 1,93 mm, desembocadura del Congo (ZMB); D: protoconcha.

evident and have the same size as the dorsal ones, but are a little flatter on the base. In *C. striatus* the base area apparently lacks any cord and has a very light and almost smooth aspect, which can be seen under strong magnification. It is possible that in the material from Arca-chon studied by Adam and Knudsen some shells of *C. striatus* with basal cords were present, due to the great

variability of the species. These shells never have stronger marked cords as does *C. congoensis*.

3- The umbilicus of *C. striatus* is more open than that of *C. congoensis*.

4- *C. striatus* is proportionally flatter than *C. congoensis*.

5- The umbilical cords in *C. striatus* are more axially sculptured than those of *C. congoensis*.

Figure 9. *Circulus congoensis* (Thiele, 1925). A-D: shells: 1.7, 1.7, 1.6, 1.6 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); E: detail of the umbilicus; F, G: protoconchs; H, I: microsculpture.

Figura 9. *Circulus congoensis* (Thiele, 1925). A-D: conchas: 1,7; 1,7; 1,6; 1,6 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); E: detalle del ombligo; F, G: protoconchas; H, I: microescultura.

Circulus senegalensis Adam and Knudsen, 1969 (Figs. 10A-F)

Circulus senegalensis Adam and Knudsen, 1969: 13, fig. 6. [Type locality: Senegal, 60 m].

Type material: Holotype and 29 paratypes in RBINS.

Other material examined: Western Sahara: Dakhla: 1 s, beach sediments (MHNS). Mauritania: 1 s, Nouakchott, fishermen dredgings, 80-100 m (CJH). Ivory Coast: 11 s, Centre Oceanographique, Abdijan, stn 13, (MNHN); 1 s, Radiale Grand Bassam R/V "Antea Benchaci I", 5° 05' N, 3° 46.6' W, 55 m (MNHN); 1 s, Radiale Gd. Bassam R/V "Antea Benchaci I", 5° 06' N, 3° 46.6' W, 50 m (MNHN). Ghana: 2 s, Miamia, 50 m (MHNS); 31 s, Miamia, 45-50 m (MHNS); 4 s, 38-40 m (MHNS); 12 s, Cap Three points, 35-65 m (MHNS). Congo: 1 s, Sta. 964, R/V André Nizery, 5° 25' S, 12° 01' E, 70 m (MNHN); 1 s, Sta. 949, R/V André Nizery, 5° 23' S, 11° 48' E, 40 m (MNHN); 5 s, Sta. 916, R/V André Nizery, 3° 4' S, 10° 13.5' E, 100 m (MNHN); 1 s, Sta. 1031, R/V André Nizery, 3° 15' S, 10° 22' E, 30 m (MNHN). Angola: 2 s, Cabinda, W Landana 5° 07' S, 12° 01' E, 9 m (MNHN); 32 s, 5 j, Mussulo, Luanda, 20-100 m (MNHN); 25 s, 50 j, Luanda, 50-70 m (MNHN); 4 s, Luanda, 100 m (MHNS).

Description: See ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969). Shell (Figs. 10A-D) flat, with 4.5 whorls, solid, whitish, reaching up to 2.8 mm in width and 1.7 mm in height.

Protoconch (Fig. 10E) multispiral with almost two whorls and a diameter of about 540 μ m. The transition to the teleoconch is difficult to see because of the lack of sculpture on this part of the surface.

The teleoconch is smooth except for the presence of three (sometimes four) umbilical cords separated by sulci, the innermost one being more developed. Axial ornamentation formed by little

sinusoidal growth lines, which when crossing the umbilical cords give them an undulating aspect only visible under strong magnification.

Aperture circular. At those points where keels appear in other species, a sinusoidal profile may be observed.

Distribution: This species is found all along the African coast from Western Sahara south to Angola.

Remarks: This species is very distinct because it is smooth on the dorsum and thus quite different from other species occurring in the area studied.

Circulus pseudopraecedens Adam and Knudsen, 1969 (Figure 11A-D)

Circulus pseudopraecedens Adam and Knudsen, 1969: 14, fig. 7. [Type locality: Grand Cess, Liberia].

Type material: Holotype and 7 paratypes in RBINS. Holotype figured in ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969).

Other material examined: Senegal: 2 j, Dakar, 20 m (MHNS); 2 s, Casamance, 12° 20.7' N, 16° 53.1' W, 15 m (MNHN); 1 s, Le Tacoma, 15 m (CJP). Ghana: 22 s, 50 j, 3 f, Miamia, 35-40 m (MHNS); 8 s, 1 j, Miamia, 40-55 m (MHNS). Equatorial Guinea: 2 s, Río Níñez, 1° 35' N, 15° 26' W, 9 m (MHNS); 1 s, W Ile Quito, R/V "André Nizery" Sedigui II, 10° 00' N, 15° 46' W, 28 m (MNHN). Angola: 7 s, Luanda, 20-100 m (MHNS).

Description: Shell (Figs. 11A-C): see ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969).

Shell circular, depressed, with 4.8 whorls (protoconch included) which reaches 3.3 mm in diameter and 1.3 mm in height. Protoconch (Fig. 11D), with a little less than 3 whorls and about 800 μ m in width. The transition to the teleoconch is difficult to see, but appears at the beginning of the upper cord. The shell has a vit-

reous, slightly transparent aspect. It has a clear peripheral keel and a spiral cord like an upper keel. In most of the shells there is no basal keel but ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969) mention that they found a shell from Rufinesque Bay with this keel.

The subsutural area is flat and smooth without subsutural cords. The upper lateral area can present some scarcely prominent narrow cords. A

Figure 10. *Circulus senegalensis* Adam and Knudsen, 1969. A, B: shells, 1.9, 2.0 mm, Abidjan, Ivory Coast (MHNS); C, D: shells, 2.1, 1.3 mm, Luanda, Angola (MNHN); E: protoconch; F: detail of the umbilical sculpture.

Figura 10. Circulus senegalensis Adam y Knudsen, 1969. A, B: conchas, 1,9; 2,0 mm, Abidjan, Costa de Marfil (MHNS); C, D: conchas, 2,1; 1,3 mm, Luanda, Angola (MNHN); E: protoconcha; F: detalle de la escultura umbilical.

Figure 11. *Circulus pseudopraecedens* Adam and Knudsen, 1969. A-C: shells, 3.2, 2.8, 3.1 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); D: protoconch.

Figura 11. *Circulus pseudopraecedens* Adam y Knudsen, 1969. A-C: conchas, 3,2; 2,8; 3,1 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MHNS); D: protoconcha.

cord, placed at $\frac{1}{3}$ between the suture and the peripheral cord appears at the beginning of the teleoconch and represents the upper keel. Below, other small cords may appear but are barely noticeable.

The peripheral keel is the most outstanding feature of the sculpture. The lateral low cords, the basal keel and the basal cords are absent or are very slight in juvenile shells. On the contrary, in adult shells, after some scars they can

appear more evidently. From a basal view the shell shows a wide and deep umbilicus. In its interior there are 5-6 umbilical cords.

When it comes to the axial microsculpture, only sinusoidal growth lines can be found.

The aperture is circular and prosocline, and from a basal view the upper

part of the external lip clearly extends beyond the lower part.

Distribution: Known from Senegal to Angola.

Remarks: The characteristic shape with constant and prominent keels and lacking other intermediate cords separates this species from other congeners in the studied area.

Circulus stephani Rolán and Ryall, 2002 (Figure 12A-F)

Circulus stephani Rolán and Ryall, 2002. *Iberus*, 20 (1): 95, figs. 1-6. [Type locality: Mimia, Ghana, 38-40 m].

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 12A) in MNCN and paratypes in several museums (MNHN, MHNS, etc.) mentioned in the original description.

Other material examined: Ivory Coast: 1 s, Abidjan Grand Bassan (col. Leboeuf Ortson) (MNHN). Ghana: 8 s, 38-40 m; (MHNS); 4 s, Cap Three Points, 35-65 m (MHNS). Angola: Cabinda: 1 s, W. Luanda 10° 05' S, 11° 59' E, 25 m; R/V André Nizery (col. MNHN) (also that mentioned in the original description).

Description: Shell (Figs. 12A-E): see ROLÁN AND RYALL (2002). Shell circular, depressed, with about 4.5 whorls reaching 2.1 mm in diameter. Protoconch (Fig. 12F) with almost 2.75 whorls and 740 µm in width. *Circulus stephani* presents three evident keels: upper, peripheral and basal. The upper one is the least developed, while the basal one is the strongest, reaching the maximum width of the shell.

The subsutural cords appear at the beginning of the teleoconch. They are

clearly narrower than the corresponding interspaces. The first one to appear will be the upper keel. Later, on the subsutural area the other four cords appear. As the shell grows in size, more cords appear, while the largest shells can have up to 10 subsutural cords.

Distribution: Known from Ivory Coast to Angola.

Remarks: See ROLÁN AND RYALL (2002) for differentiation from other species of the genus in West Africa.

Circulus microsculpturatus spec. nov. (Figures 13A-F)

Type material: Holotype in MNHN (23687) (Figs. 13A-B). Paratype; 1 s, Dakhla, 50 m, Western Sahara in MNCN (15.05/55052).

Type locality: Sediments trawled at 50 m, Guinea Conakry.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the microsculpture characteristic of the present species.

Description: Shell (Fig. 13A-B) circular, depressed, solid, with almost 4.5 whorls, reaches 3.5 mm in diameter and 1.5 mm in height. Protoconch (Fig. 13C) with 2 whorls and 510 µm in diameter. The main sculpture is formed by spiral cords, narrower than the corresponding interspaces. In these interspaces appears a granular microsculpture which is characteristic of this species

(Figs. 13D-F). Three of the cords are more developed forming keels: upper, peripheral and basal. The basal one is particularly developed, giving a rectangular appearance to the peristome. Between the suture and the upper keel there are 5-6 spiral cords. Between the upper and the peripheral keels there are 23 cords, of which the upper one is nearly as large as the keel itself.

Figure 12. *Circulus stephani* Rolán and Ryall, 2002. A: holotype, 2.1 mm (MNCN); B: paratype, 1.7 mm (MNHN); C: paratype, 2.0 mm (AMNH); D: paratype, 1.6 mm (NHMUK); E: paratype, 2.1 mm (MHNS); F: protoconch of the holotype.

Figura 12. *Circulus stephani* Rolán y Ryall, 2002. A: holotipo, 2,1 mm (MNCN); B: paratipo, 1,7 mm (MNHN); C: paratipo, 2,0 mm (AMNH); D: paratipo, 1,6 mm (NHMUK); E: paratipo, 2,1 mm (MHNS); F: protoconcha del holotipo.

Between the peripheral and the basal keels there are four cords. There is not a clear basal cord, the base being occupied by about 14 cordlets with a width similar to that of the interspaces. They go into the umbilicus.

Distribution: Only known from the type material (From Sahara to Guinea Conakry).

Remarks: The microsculpture of the present species differentiates it from the other congeneric species in the studied area.

Figure 13. *Circulus microsculpturatus* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, 3.4 mm, Guinea Conakry (MNHN); C: protoconch of the holotype; D-F: microsculpture.

Figura 13. *Circulus microsculpturatus* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, 3,4 mm, Guinea Conakry (MNHN); C: protoconcha del holotipo; D-F: microescultura.

Circulus ryalli spec. nov. (Figure 14A-D)

Circulus striatus in Adam and Knudsen (1969): 10, fig. 4.

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 14A) in MNCN (15.05/55053). Paratypes in the following: MNHN (23688) (1 s, Fig. 14B), MHNS (5 s, 1 j, Fig. 14C), CPR (1 s).

Type locality: Miamia, Ghana, in sediments dredged in 38-45 m.

Etymology: The species is named after Peter Ryall, a malacologist who lived for many years in Ghana and helped us during the collection of the type material.

Description: Shell (Figs. 14A-C) circular, depressed, with 4.6 whorls (protoconch included), reaching 1.9 mm in diameter and 0.9 mm in height. Protoconch (Fig. 14D) smooth, with 2 ½ whorls, and about 510 µm in diameter. Teleoconch with slightly prosocline spiral cords and axial growth lines which cross the interspaces, giving them a striated appearance. The shell has a clear peripheral keel, and in the places which would correspond to the other keels there are somewhat developed cords; as the shell increases in size the basal cord progressively becomes keel-shaped. The subsutural area is flat with six or seven cords which appear after the protoconch scar. These cords are wider than their interspaces at the beginning, but subsequently the interspaces increase in size while the cords continue the same, so that at the end of the spire the cords are clearly narrower than their interspaces. Among the subsutural cords, the adapical one is a little wider and placed in the position of the upper keel. The upper lateral area is flat and so the transition has an angled aspect (about 100°). Between the upper cord/keel and the peripheral keel, there are 6-7 cords and, with the shell in lateral view, they seem to be flatter and wider than the corresponding interspaces. In the upper lip one or two cords are inserted on the peripheral keel. The lateral lower area does not have cords and is slightly concave. The basal area is flat with 4-5 cords, two of which are more developed, in the position of the perium-

bilical cord/keel and 2-3 lighter, in the transition with the umbilical area. Between these two groups of cords there is a wide space. The umbilicus is open and in its interior there are about 7-8 spiral cords as wide as the interspaces, crossed by growth lines which give them a striated aspect.

Dimensions: the holotype is 1.97 mm.

Distribution: Only known from the type material.

Remarks: This species appears to be that which ADAM AND KNUDSEN (1969) considered as *C. striatus* from Iles de Los, to the W of Crawford Bank.

Circulus striatus lacks true cords at the base which is smooth; in the umbilical cords, there is a typical microsculpture while in *C. ryalli* there only appear fine axial growth lines; the protoconch of *C. striatus* has between 2 and a little more whorls, with 390 µm in diameter, while *C. ryalli* has a protoconch with 2 ½ whorls and about 510 µm. The beginning of the teleoconch in *C. ryalli* shows evident cords, all similar, while those in *C. striatus* are generally more attenuate and the subsutural one has constantly visible microsculpture.

Circulus senegalensis has a smooth shell lacking keels and cords.

Circulus pseudopraecedens has keels but not spiral cords between them.

Circulus smithi has fewer cords on the dorsal part, the space between the keels being more occupied by cords.

Circulus microsculpturatus spec. nov. has a more evident microsculpture over the entire shell.

REMARKS AND FINAL DISCUSSION

Eight species of the genus *Circulus* from the East Atlantic area have been

studied in the present work. Most of the species have a tropical distribution,

Figure 14. *Circulus ryalli* spec. nov. A: holotype, 1.97 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MNC); B: paratype, 1.9 mm (MNHN); C: paratype, 1.9 mm (MHNS); D: protoconch of the holotype.

Figura 14. *Circulus ryalli* spec. nov. A: holotipo, 1,97 mm, Miamia, Ghana (MNC); B: paratipo, 1,9 mm (MNHN); C: paratipo, 1,9 mm (MHNS); D: protoconcha del holotipo.

from West Sahara south to Angola, which seems to be an area in common to all of them although not all (mainly the ones of which less material is available)

have been collected throughout the entire area.

Of those, the oldest and type species of the genus is *C. striatus*. This species

extends from the cold waters of northern Europe south to the temperate waters of the Mediterranean and northern and western Morocco. It is not present in the rest of the African west coast but has been erroneously confused with other species on several occasions.

As is usual in species with a wide dispersal area, all of them have multi-spiral protoconchs (between 2 and 3 spiral whorls).

Some European taxa which have been included in *Circulus* and do not belong there are the following:

Adeorbis subcarinatus Montagu, 1803, now considered as a species of the genus *Tornus*.

Circulus jeffreysii Monterosato, 1872: according to WARÉN (1992) it is a Skeneid species, not a *Circulus*.

Circulus formosissimus Brugnone, 1873. Synonymized with *Circulus jeffreysii*.

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